

Chukchee

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Entry tags: Circumpolar Religions, Religion

The Chukchee are indigenous to what is now known as the Chukotka Autonomous Okrug of Russia (established 1930), the Lower Kolyma District of the Yakut Republic, and the northern Koryak Autonomous Okrug. The Chukchee are divided into two economic-cultural groups: the nomadic reindeer herders, and the sedentary coastal-dwellers. This entry focuses on the reindeer division of the Chukchee around the time of 1900, and considers the Chukchee religious group to be coterminous with the society at large. Religious beliefs were bound up with the functioning of society as a whole; religious ceremonies, for example, overlap with subsistence, economic, and social activities. The religious beliefs center on shamanism. Shamans serve to communicate with spirits, perform divining rituals, produce incantations, lead ceremonies, and act as healers. A variety of supernatural beings are present.

Date Range: 1885 CE - 1910 CE

Region: Reindeer division of the Chukchee, Northeastern Russia

Region tags: Europe, Eastern Europe, Russia

Reindeer division of the Chukchee, Northeastern Russia (Kolyma district, Kamchatka, Anadyr, and the Chukchee Peninsula) ca. 1900

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: *Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: *Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ry02-001>
- Source 1 Description: Bogoraz-Tan, W., Vladimir Germanovich (Bogoras). (1904, 1907, 1909). *Chukchee*:

Material Culture [Part 1, 1904], Religion [Part 2, 1907], Social Organization [Part 3, 1909]. Memoirs. Leiden: E. J. Brill, Ltd. ; G. E. Stechert and Co.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ry02-000>

– Source 2 Description: Zhornitskaya, M., & Wanner, V. (1996). Culture Summary: Chukchee. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Intercourse with the Chukchee, renewed in 1789, was carried on the whole time with much circumspection, and no new attempt was made to conquer the Chukchee by force. The border divisions of the tribe have gradually submitted to Russian influence. The bulk of the Chukchee territory, however, up to the present time, remains practically exempt from any trace of Russianization; and there are many camps and villages where a Russian face has never been seen, nor a word of the Russian language heard" (Bogoras, 1909:15).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), indicates that internal warfare seems to occur between almost constantly and at any time of the year, and every year but usually only during a particular season (original code 4.5). Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), originally coded as 1.25, which is between "external warfare seems to be absent or rare" (original code 1), and "external warfare seems to occur once every three to ten years (original code 2). Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society at large, there is no process for assigning religious affiliation aside from being born into a particular lineage.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the recruitment of new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Chukchee religious beliefs and activities are tied up with the functioning of societies at large; the religious group is coterminous with the society at large. (e.g., religious ceremonies overlap with other aspects of life such as games, reindeer herding, and hunting) Therefore, the religion can be considered to have official political support.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: No formal political office is present (SCCS Variable, 1740, Levels of political hierarchy; Lang, 1998; Retrieved from Divale, 2004)

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: No formal political office is present (SCCS Variable, 1740, Levels of political hierarchy; Lang, 1998; Retrieved from Divale, 2004)

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of legal code.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 8000

Notes: "The whole number of reindeer camps amounts to about 650, with a population of 7500-9000, rather more than less" (Bogoras, 1909:27).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The basic and most important function of the shaman was healing. With the help of a tambourine and singing, the shaman made contact with protective spirits and with the spirits of the ancestors, and at the same time he exerted an influence over the psyche of those present. The shaman participated in almost all festivals and ceremonies when shamanistic séances were organized" (Zhornitskaya and Wanner, 1996).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence suggesting that there is a hierarchy among Chukchee shamans.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Shamans can communicate with spirits, serve as diviners, and produce incantations (see Bogoras, 1909:430, 441).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of reincarnation.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: "Most of the shamans I knew claimed to have had no teachers, but to have acquired their art by their own individual efforts. I am not aware of a single instance of the transfer of shamanistic power in the whole domain of Chukchee folklore" (Bogoras, 1909:425).

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: "Most of the shamans I knew claimed to have had no teachers, but to have acquired their art by their own individual efforts. I am not aware of a single instance of the transfer of shamanistic power in the whole domain of Chukchee folklore" (Bogoras, 1909:425).

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: Individuals become shamans after experiencing a shamanistic call, which can take the form of an inner voice or call from the spirits, or various omens such as meeting certain animals or finding a stone or shell of peculiar form (see Bogoras, 1909:418-419).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scriptures among the Chukchee.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972, column 6; note, identical to SCCS Variable 66).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972, column 6; note, identical to SCCS Variable 66).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic information on the Chukchee's beliefs in the afterlife provides evidence for the presence of a spirit-body distinction. "The Aurora Borealis is chiefly the place of abode for those who die a sudden or violent death. The whitish spots are the people who died from contagious diseases; the red spots are those stabbed with a knife; the dark spots are those strangled by the 'spirits' of nervous diseases; the changeable rays are deceased people running about and playing ball with a walrus-head which is alive...Another way for the dead to ascend to heaven is to follow the smoke of their funeral

pyre" (Bogoras, 1909:334). "Deceased women who have no husbands go to a world of their own. They live there, catching reindeer with nooses and nets as they come to cross Pebbly River. Their world is situated in the lower portion of the sky, and it is much less important than the first upper world" (Bogoras, 1909:335).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "There are several places where the deceased abide. They lead a life similar to that on earth. They are often confounded with the Upper People, or with the Lower People of the underground world" (Bogoras, 1909:333-334).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The Aurora Borealis is chiefly the place of abode for those who die a sudden or violent death. The whitish spots are the people who died from contagious diseases; the red spots are those stabbed with a knife; the dark spots are those strangled by the 'spirits' of nervous diseases; the changeable rays are deceased people running about and playing ball with a walrus-head which is alive...Another way for the dead to ascend to heaven is to follow the smoke of their funeral pyre" (Bogoras, 1909:334). "Deceased women who have no husbands go to a world of their own. They live there, catching reindeer with nooses and nets as they come to cross Pebbly River. Their world is situated in the lower portion of the sky, and it is much less important than the first upper world" (Bogoras, 1909:335).

Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "While some of the dead are in these upper worlds, the usual place of abode for the deceased is underground. Their country is very extensive, and full of intricate paths which puzzle new-comers" (Bogoras, 1909:335).

Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "While some of the dead are in these upper worlds, the usual place of abode for the deceased is underground. Their country is very extensive, and full of intricate paths which puzzle new-comers" (Bogoras, 1909:335).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnations.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "For this the Chukchee generally have two methods,--either by burning the body on a funeral

pyre, or by carrying it away and leaving it, on the ground in the wilderness. Most of the Maritime people and of the reindeer-breeders of the Chukchee Peninsula use, of course, the second method; while the villages lying close to large accumulations of driftwood--as, for instance, those on Cape Erri and also those of the reindeer-breeders of the Anui and Anadyr--both burn and expose their corpses. Each family, however, uses one and the same method from generation to generation" (Bogoras, 1909:522-523).

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "Another way for the dead to ascend to heaven is to follow the smoke of their funeral pyre. This is given as a reason for burning dead bodies" (Bogoras, 1909:334).

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of internment.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: "For this the Chukchee generally have two methods,--either by burning the body on a funeral pyre, or by carrying it away and leaving it, on the ground in the wilderness. Most of the Maritime people and of the reindeer-breeders of the Chukchee Peninsula use, of course, the second method; while the villages lying close to large accumulations of driftwood--as, for instance, those on Cape Erri and also those of the reindeer-breeders of the Anui and Anadyr--both burn and expose their corpses. Each family, however, uses one and the same method from generation to generation" (Bogoras, 1909:522-523).

↳ Feeding to animals:

– I don't know

Notes: The bodies of the deceased are either cremated or left outside in the wilderness (Bogoras, 1909:522-523). It does not appear that bodies are left outside with the primary intention of them being fed to animals, but presumably, animals will feed on the corpse.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, indicates that among the Chukchee, secondary bone/body treatment is absent (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of re-treatment of corpses.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of grave goods.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Among the Chukchee, the deceased are cremated or exposed to the elements. No formal burials take place.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Various types of supernatural beings are present among the Chukchee. See questions below for more information.

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [Note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas column 34], indicates that a high god is present and active in human affairs, but not specifically supportive of human morality (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Chukchee.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Chukchee.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Another important seeming contradiction refers to the influence which the deceased may have on the good or bad fortune of living human beings. One line of native thought is inclined to consider the deceased as benevolent protectors of their descendants. Some details in the arrangement of the household charm-string.... show elements of a real cult of ancestors" (Bogoras, 1909:336).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "As has been said before, deceased persons are regarded by the Chukchee as working in a two fold capacity, --that of benevolent protectors and assistants, and that of dangerous beings, very near to the ke'let [JMR: harmful spirits], who, even when they mean well, may cause only harm to the living" (Bogoras, 1909:516).

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "As has been said before, deceased persons are regarded by the Chukchee as working in a two fold capacity, --that of benevolent protectors and assistants, and that of dangerous beings, very near to the ke'let [JMR: harmful spirits], who, even when they mean well, may cause only harm to the living" (Bogoras, 1909:516).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Various classes of animals and trees also have their 'masters,' who live in the forest with them. Each species of tree has a separate 'master.' The birch alone has none, and for that reason, men handle it without precaution, as 'their equal.' The latter conception is clearly connected with the yearly expeditions of the Reindeer Chukchee into the woods to procure birch, of which they make their sledges, the shafts of spears, etc. Each species of wild animal--fox, wolf, reindeer--has a 'master' of its own. The Chukchee often call all these 'masters' simply 'spirits' (ke'let). This latter term is specially applied to spirits of a harmful kind, of which I shall treat farther on in this chapter; but the Chukchee apply it also to the 'masters,' implying that these 'spirits' are harmless" (Bogoras, 1909:285-286). "The ke'let [JMR: evil spirits] proper may be divided into three classes more or less distinct, though often merging into one another. The first class consists of evil spirits who walk about invisibly, bringing disease and death, and preying on human souls and bodies. The second category is made up of blood-thirsty cannibals who lived, or still live, somewhere on the distant shores, and always fight against the Chukchee warriors. The third class includes the 'spirits' that come at the call of the shamans, and help them in their magic and medical practices" (Bogoras, 1909:291-292).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

— Yes

Notes: "The shamanistic 'spirits' are very ill tempered, especially toward the shaman with whom they are connected. If he does not carry out implicitly all the suggestions they make about his dress, mode of living, and the details of ceremonials, they become angry and chastise him, or punish him otherwise. If he continues to disobey, they kill him. If the 'spirits' are displeased with any of the listeners at a ceremony, they usually take vengeance on the shaman. For this reason, outsiders must be very quiet, and careful not to pry into the work of the 'spirits'" (Bogoras, 1909:302).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

— Yes

Notes: (Bogoras, 1909:302).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

— Yes

Notes: "Pi cvu'cin is a special 'owner' of wild reindeer and of all land-game. He lives in deep ravines, and stays near the forest-border. From there he sends reindeer-herds to the hunters; but when he is angered he withholds the supply. He is especially strict in demanding the performance of all ancient customs and sacrifices connected with the hunt, and resents every slight neglect of them. He is represented as very small, not larger than a man's finger, and his footprints on the snow are like those of a mouse" (Bogoras, 1909:286-287).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

— Yes

Notes: "Supernatural beings which are benevolent in nature are called 'beings' (va'IrgIt)" (Bogoras, 1909:303).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The ke'let [JMR: evil spirits] proper may be divided into three classes more or less distinct, though often merging into one another. The first class consists of evil spirits who walk about invisibly, bringing disease and death, and preying on human souls and bodies. The second category is made up of blood-thirsty cannibals who lived, or still live, somewhere on the distant shores, and always fight against the Chukchee warriors" (Bogoras, 1909:291-292).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits are present among the Chukchee, as well as various types of non-human supernatural beings (see questions above).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "The shamanistic 'spirits' are very ill tempered, especially toward the shaman with whom they are connected. If he does not carry out implicitly all the suggestions they make about his dress, mode of living, and the details of ceremonials, they become angry and chastise him, or punish him otherwise. If he continues to disobey, they kill him. If the 'spirits' are displeased with any of the listeners at a ceremony, they usually take vengeance on the shaman. For this reason, outsiders must be very quiet, and careful not to pry into the work of the 'spirits'" (Bogoras, 1909:302). Aside from these shamanistic spirits, it does not appear that other supernatural beings are concerned with the affairs of humanity. Therefore, little ethnographic information concerning supernatural monitoring is available.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: "The shamanistic 'spirits' are very ill tempered, especially toward the shaman with whom they are connected. If he does not carry out implicitly all the suggestions they make about his dress, mode of living, and the details of ceremonials, they become angry and chastise him, or punish him otherwise. If he continues to disobey, they kill him. If the 'spirits' are displeased with any of the listeners at a ceremony, they usually take vengeance on the shaman. For this reason, outsiders must be very quiet, and careful not to pry into the work of the 'spirits'" (Bogoras, 1909:302).

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: "The shamanistic 'spirits' are very ill tempered, especially toward the shaman with whom they are connected. If he does not carry out implicitly all the suggestions they make about his dress, mode of living, and the details of ceremonials, they become angry and

chastise him, or punish him otherwise. If he continues to disobey, they kill him. If the 'spirits' are displeased with any of the listeners at a ceremony, they usually take vengeance on the shaman. For this reason, outsiders must be very quiet, and careful not to pry into the work of the 'spirits'" (Bogoras, 1909:302).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Shamanistic spirits mete out punishment (Bogoras, 1909:302). It does not appear that other supernatural beings are involved with supernatural punishment. Therefore, little ethnographic information concerning supernatural punishment is available.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information on the reasons for supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: "The shamanistic 'spirits' are very ill tempered, especially toward the shaman with whom they are connected. If he does not carry out implicitly all the suggestions they make about his dress, mode of living, and the details of ceremonials, they become angry and chastise him, or punish him otherwise. If he continues to disobey, they kill him. If the 'spirits' are displeased with any of the listeners at a ceremony, they usually take vengeance on the shaman. For this reason, outsiders must be very quiet, and careful not to pry into the work of the 'spirits'" (Bogoras, 1909:302).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence supporting the presence of supernatural punishment in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishment occurs in this life, but is not described in detail. "The shamanistic 'spirits' are very ill tempered, especially toward the shaman with whom they are connected. If he does not carry out implicitly all the suggestions they make about his dress, mode of living, and the details of ceremonials, they become angry and chastise him, or punish him otherwise. If he continues to disobey, they kill him. If the 'spirits' are displeased with any of the listeners at a ceremony, they usually take vengeance on the shaman. For this reason, outsiders must be very quiet, and careful not to pry into the work of the 'spirits'" (Bogoras, 1909:302).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "There are several restrictions connected with animal food. The Reindeer Chukchee abstain from the meat of the wolverene and black bear, of all the species of Canis, and of most birds of prey. The large owl of the tundra (*Strix nyctea*) and its large eggs are eaten. Milt of reindeer is supposed to cause the impotency of men and the flabby breasts of women, and is tabooed for young people of both sexes. The same taboo exists concerning the tongue and the gastrocnemius muscle of the sacrificed fawn" (Bogoras, 1909:196).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds are required.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Notes: "Each family.... has its peculiar groups of images and ceremonials, characterized by special details, and differing from those used by neighboring families. These differences develop continually under orders received from shamans, or directly from spirits through dreams. In this way, even the chief ceremonials of the year come to be observed somewhat differently by neighboring camps and by different families in the same villages" (Bogoras, 1909:338).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Communal ceremonies are held for the slaughtering of reindeer, but participation does not appear to be mandatory (see Bogoras, 1909:370-380). It appears that most ceremonies are held at the family-level.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Chukchee have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, according to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent) "descent

is bilateral, i.e., ancestor-oriented descent groups are absent, and kinsmen are aggregated only by consanguineal and/or affinal ties between individuals, as in personal kindreds or kiths." Further, The Chukchee have agamous communities without localized clans or any marked tendency toward either local exogamy or local endogamy; patrilineal and matrilineal kin groups and exogamy are both absent. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967), Columns 19, 20, 22.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient evidence

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The Chukchee have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that among the Chukchee, routes of land transport included unimproved trails (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of taxation.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "Police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery" (Column 10: Police; Tuden and Marshall, 1972).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "Supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community" (Column 9: Judiciary; Tuden and Marshall, 1972).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Chukchee rely primarily on animal husbandry, with hunting and fishing providing additional sources of subsistence. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

Notes: The Chukchee rely primarily on animal husbandry, with hunting and fishing providing additional sources of subsistence. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.